

THE ROLE OF THE MODULAR CREDIT SYSTEM STUDENT TRAINING UNIVERSITY

Khaidarova Khatich Ramizovna

Samarkand State Medical University,

Department Assistant of Pediatrics, Faculty of Medicine,

Marupov Shukhrat Nasimovich

Lecturer at the Department of Russian Language and Literature

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign

languages.

Allayarova Dilfuza Klychevna

Teacher of the department of Uzbek, Russian language and literature.
Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry
and Biotechnology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7805824>

ABSTRACT

The introduction of a credit-accumulative system is not only gives greater freedom to the student, but also allows him to plan educational process so that in the future it can become competitive professional in the chosen sphere. At the same time, it contributes improvement of the assessment system and educational technologies.

Key words Modular learning, module, educational element, rating, loans, academic loans.

Today, when in all spheres the life of the country are taking place fundamental changes, reforms in higher education are important meaning. Among the most relevant - transition of education to credit modular system. At the videoconference,

held on June 16 of this year and dedicated to priorities in system of higher education, chapter states designated four priority in this direction: enhance the role of governing boards and expand the powers of the departments of higher educational institutions; bring the learning process into compliance with market requirements, link it to production and create an environment where students can work on yourself; increase the scientific potential of universities, continue the development of science and innovation; cut paperwork teachers and students, and bureaucracy and corruption

digitalization of the sphere. In addition, the President instructed officials to bring state educational standards in line with international, translate educational process in all universities for credit-modular system. Necessary revise content subjects taught: eliminate duplication and increase the number profile (specialized). It is noted that for effective fulfillment of these tasks the highest educational institutions will be given authority to take independent solutions for academic and organizational management. In other words, from now on the council of the university follows its decisions on curriculum and literature, implementation of scientific projects, workload of professors and teachers and defining forms learning.

It is shown that the activity each department is evaluated based on its potential and involvement youth in scientific work. Apart from this, the task optimize the list of professions, requiring a higher education, and introduce new specialties in demand sectors of the economy. Transition to credit-modular the system will be further enlarged need for digital technologies.

It is worth noting here that in 2020 year the Cabinet of Ministers adopted resolution "On measures to system improvement organization of educational process in higher education institutions." According to the document from 2020/2021 academic year process education in universities is gradually being transferred on the credit-modular system (KMS). But what is it? This European university system education (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System - ECTS), which provides for the following:

- Modular structure educational program. Educational material on a particular specialties are divided into separate blocks are modules. student studies subject/module within its specialties in forced mode: lectures and practical classes in this subject are every day until it is delivered to exam or test. Increasing Flexibility

educational programs. IN depending on the minimum or advanced level of training the student takes some amount hours per subject. Student participation in formation of individual curriculum. Everyone has their own personal plan with specific a set of courses and choose which one them to take first, and which one later. Increasing the share of self-learning in educational process. A number of topics given for independent study. Students prepare creative work (abstracts, presentations), study additional literature, recommended by the teacher delve deeper into their area of interest. Use of credits (credits) to assess the complexity. The use of scores rating systems for assessing knowledge. Currently in higher education institutions of the country carried out a number measures for the gradual transfer of educational process on the KMS. Transformations take place at our university.

Smooth transition to credit-modular system in TSUE is in the following: involved in the educational process more than 30 foreign and domestic professors and teachers; held master classes on CMS in universities of Uzbekistan; curricula are used and 1st year undergraduate programs and master's programs developed on the basis of foreign experience with the involvement international experts; the book "Credit-modular system ECTS in higher educational institutions of the Republic Uzbekistan: basic concepts and rules", published jointly with the Foundation

"El-yurt umidi", Republican Council of Higher Education and Tashkent State economic university; selected for CMS training high level teachers preparation.

Introduction of the accumulation system loans not only gives the student greater freedom, but also allows plan your own study process so that in the future it can become competitive professional in the selected area. At the same time it contributes to the improvement assessment systems and educational technologies. The introduction of CMS in the field of higher education education will improve the quality training, provide transparency, eliminate corruption, expose true knowledge of the student and will create the basis for independent getting knowledge and work.

In addition, the introduction of credit-modular system is an important factor in cooperation between teacher and student. Thus, the teacher organizes guides, advises, checks learning process listener.

However, the greatest emphasis done on self-study students, which means that it increases importance in the learning process. This lead to increased creativity initiatives and activities professionals. In the CCM, university students always have opportunity to get help or advice from teachers and classmates, which strengthens

mutual understanding and promote development of teamwork skills. Moreover, the transition to credit-modular training system will increase interest and demand for professors and higher education teachers establishments. As mentioned above, when such an innovation teacher consistently performs not only information and control functions, but also advisory and coordinating. Saved it leading role in education process. It is important that this system focused on professional student development and maturity, and ensuring continuous learning..

References:

1. Yutsyavichene P. A. Theory and practice of modular education. Kaunas, 1989. 271 p.
2. Danilson T. S., Rumbeshta E. A. Modular-activity approach in teaching physics // Vestn. Tomsk State ped. university No. 10. 2010.S. 35-38
3. Lezhnina L. V., Shishkovsky V. I. Scoring system as a factor increasing students' motivation for learning activities // Vestn. Tomsk State ped. university No. 7. 2009. S. 91-94.
4. Pedagogy: Great modern encyclopedia / comp. E. S. Rapatsevich. Minsk: "Modern. word", 2005. 720 p.
5. Final document of the international scientific conference "Experience of international cooperation between Russian universities: the Bologna process and the concept modernization of education". Yekaterinburg, March 10-12, 2003
6. Nasyrova E. F., Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department. Surgut State University.
7. История развития системы кредитного модуля, механизм получения знаний учащимися. Saodat Narzullaevna Sattorova Lecturer, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages. Volume: 32|2023. P 189-191.
8. Ex. Lenina, 1, Surgut, Tyumen region, Russia, 628400. E-mail: elm.n@mail.ru
9. Тиббиёт олийгохларида укув жараённинг сифатини ошириш мақсадида тизимли ва жараёнли ёндошув. ЛМ Гарифулина, ЗЭ Холмурадова, ГН Кудратова, ДС Ибрагимова . «Современное состояние, проблемы и перспективы медицинского образования» международная учебно-научно-практическая конференция «тиббий таълимнинг замонавий ҳолати»
10. The material was received by the editors on 11/01/2010. E. F. Nasyrova

